

Progress and difficulty in gaining regulatory acceptance of PBPK modeling and mechanism of toxicity in risk assessments

Harvey Clewell

Ramboll

Abstract

The practice of risk assessment, like the science of toxicology upon which it relies, is in a continuous process of evolution and refinement. As new experimental methods become available that show a potential to more accurately or efficiently characterize the toxicity of chemicals, they must be carefully evaluated by both scientists and regulatory officials to ensure they are an effective and reliable alternative to traditional approaches. Physiologically Based Kinetic (PBK) modeling is one of the more mature New Approach Methods, having been applied in regulatory decisions for nearly 40 years, and yet gaining regulatory agency acceptance of the use of a PBK model in a regulatory decision is still fraught with difficulty. This presentation will describe a number of recent modeling efforts that were conducted to foster the application of PBK in chemical risk assessments, and will discuss some of the factors that can make the regulatory acceptance of such applications so problematic.